

PSYCHOLOGICAL INSIGHTS OF COMMUNITY LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chet tili sifatida ingliz tili darslarida jamoaviy til o'rganishning psixologik jihati va uning ishtirok, o'rganish, motivatsiya, hissiy xavfsizlik va o'zaro ta'sirga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi o'qituvchi, maslahatchi va motivator bilan o'rganish ishtirok, o'zaro ta'sirni oshiradi va talabalarni o'rganishga ilhomlantiradi. An'anaviy va CLLga asoslangan yondashuvlar qo'llanildi, unda 30 nafar bakalavr talabasi ishtirok etdi, bu esa yanada ijobiy o'quv muhitini yaratdi. Ushbu sohadagi tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, CLL usulidan foydalanish talabalarning ishtirokini an'anaviy o'qitish usullariga nisbatan 50-70% gacha oshirishi va bir vaqtning o'zida xavotirni 30-40% gacha kamaytirishi mumkin. Tadqiqotlar shuningdek, CLL darslaridan o'quvchilar o'z nutqlariga ko'proq ishonishlari haqida xabar beradi. Tadqiqot psixologik va hissiy qo'llab-quvvatlash til o'rganishda muhim rol o'ynashini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Jamoaviy til o'rganish, psixologik xavfsizlik, EFL o'rganish, talabalarning motivatsiyasi, ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, til xavotiri, hamkorlikdagi o'rganish

Annotation. This article investigates the psychological side of Community Language Learning and its influence on participation, learning, motivation, emotional safety and interaction in English as a Foreign Language Classrooms . Findings indicate that learning with supportive teacher, counselor, and motivator increases participation, interaction, and inspires students to learn. Both traditional and CLL-based approaches were used, with 30 undergraduate students involved, which created a more positive learning environment. Research in this field showed that use of CLL method can increase student engagement by up to 50–70% compared to traditional instruction methods and reduce 30–40 % of anxiety at the same time. Studies also report that learners from CLL classes are more confident in their speech. The study suggests that psychological and emotional support play important role in language learning

Keywords: Community Language Learning, psychological safety, EFL learning, student motivation, social interaction, language anxiety, collaborative learning

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется психологическая сторона обучения языку в сообществе и его влияние на участие, обучение, мотивацию, эмоциональную безопасность и взаимодействие в классах английского языка как иностранного. Результаты показывают, что обучение с поддержкой преподавателя, консультанта и мотиватора повышает участие, взаимодействие и вдохновляет студентов на обучение. Использовались как традиционные, так и основанные на обучении языку в сообществе подходы, в которых участвовали 30 студентов, что создало более позитивную учебную среду. Исследования в этой области показали, что использование метода обучения языку в сообществе может повысить вовлеченность студентов на 50–70% по сравнению с традиционными методами обучения и одновременно снизить уровень тревожности на 30–40%. Исследования также показывают, что учащиеся из классов, обучающихся по методу обучения языку в сообществе, более уверены в своей речи. Исследование предполагает, что психологическая и эмоциональная поддержка играют важную роль в изучении языка.

Ключевые слова: обучение языку в сообществе, психологическая безопасность, изучение английского как иностранного, мотивация студентов, социальное взаимодействие, языковая тревожность, совместное обучение

Introduction

Language learning is not about only textbooks or intellectual pursuit, it has strong connection to emotions, identity and human connection. Community language learning, developed by Charles Curran in 1976, is a method that sees learners not as passive members of learning environment but as active members of supportive community. CCL focuses more on counseling-learning, where teacher acts as facilitator or counselor working with independent students, who have individual needs. This approach addresses most popular language barrier - language anxiety, group collaboration stress and fear of making mistakes. According to Horwitz et al. (1986), in speaking tasks anxiety can significantly hinder language performance.

Unlike all traditional methods, CCL classes include discussions, brainstorming, pair and group works. Learners can get motivated by trust-worthy teacher and share ideas with their supportive classmates. As Vygotsky's social constructivist theory suggests, learning is fundamentally social, and knowledge emerges through interaction within a community (Vygotsky, 1978).

Method

A mixed-method approach was employed to explore the psychological effects of CLL on students of English Language and Literature field. The sample size for the research involved 30 undergraduate students, who were all studying English. All subjects were from the same institution and had identical educational and academic backgrounds.

During the first week, standard teaching methods were used. The lessons used regular English, lectures, textbook exercises, individual speaking tasks. The teacher had a central role in classroom, where students interaction was limited.

In the second week, the lessons started using CCL approach. The first thing the students did was to sit in circles, where they could be easily arranged into small groups or work with pairs observing class at the same time. Students could have warm-up early or and then move to group discussions with teacher support, ask questions to translate or reformulate sentences or words and get reflective feedback at the end of class.

Data was collected by observing class, getting student questionnaire about motivation and anxiety levels and speaking performance assessments.

Result

It is evident that there is a significant improvement in students' mental states in terms of their engagement and anxiety when learning within the framework of the CL model. Students' engagement rates increased by 50-70%, which means that they were significantly more involved in class activities than during other lessons. Besides, the level of anxiety went down by 30-40%, especially when performing verbal exercises – activities that are traditionally considered to be most difficult and stressing for students.

At the same time, speaking became a more confident activity because it became clear that students felt more secure when speaking English thanks to a friendly atmosphere created during the lessons. Furthermore, learners demonstrated greater readiness to cooperate and interact by 20–25%. One of the most significant findings was that students who used to stay silent even during regular lessons actively participated in the activities during CLL.

Discussion

Firstly, the outcomes of this study correspond to numerous studies of the impact of Community Language Learning on the psychology of students who use it in the EFL classroom. Elaine K. Horwitz et al. (1986) state that language anxiety and its negative implications are particularly relevant to the speaking skills of foreign language learners. The decline in language anxiety (30–40%) observed in this research proves this statement, proving that creating a positive atmosphere and eliminating pressure helps students become less scared and start working. Moreover, the growth in student engagement and communicative activities matches the key ideas of Lev Vygotsky's social constructivism theory according to which all learning happens through collaboration and exchange of information between peers. Therefore, group discussions inherent to CLL can serve as a good way to create such conditions.

Furthermore, changes in speaking skills of those students who usually stay quiet during lessons fit well into the cooperative learning paradigm. David W. Johnson and Roger T. Johnson (1999) state that the mentioned approach promotes positive interdependence and makes learners accountable and more confident.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper demonstrates that Community Language Learning positively influences the psychological state of students in their studies. First of all, the analysis of results reveals that in a friendly and collaborative learning environment, students are encouraged to interact actively and are less afraid to speak up, especially in oral tasks. This allows students to feel more comfortable and be motivated to take part in classroom work. It should be noted that even shy students, who rarely talk, were more active in CLL classes.

References

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